

Pedestal-free 7-rod-core Tm-doped fiber for fiber lasers

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Abstract: Structured-core thulium-doped fibers were developed to reduce heat load, enable shorter-wavelength operation, and achieve a pedestal-free design. In a proof-of-principle experiment, laser slope efficiencies of 52% at 1907 nm and 54% at 1940 nm were achieved with respect to absorbed power.

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1. Introduction

Thulium-doped fiber lasers (TDFLs) and amplifiers emitting near 2 μm in the eye-safe infrared region are widely used in medicine, sensing, and frequency conversion because of their low risk of retinal damage and strong water absorption [1]. They can be efficiently pumped at 0.79 μm using commercial diodes that excite the $^3\text{H}_4$ energy level. Although the Stokes limit restricts the theoretical efficiency to about 40%, TDFLs benefit from a cross-relaxation “2-for-1” process ($^3\text{H}_4, ^3\text{H}_6 \rightarrow ^3\text{F}_4, ^3\text{F}_4$) enabled by high thulium ion (Tm^{3+}) concentrations (>7000 ppm), which significantly enhances laser efficiency [2]. TDFLs utilize a wide emission range of 1.6–2.2 μm , enabling various applications depending on the chosen wavelength. At a wavelength range of 1.62–1.66 μm , TDF with Tm-co-doped silica enables U-band amplification, expanding telecom capabilities beyond erbium-based systems [3,4]. In the 1.7–1.9 μm range, Tm-fibers are investigated as mode-locked sources that generate high-energy, ultrafast pulses suitable for bioimaging and industrial applications [5]. The widely used range is 1.9–2.05 μm , where high-gain, efficient diode pumping supports high-power CW and pulsed lasers for materials processing, sensing, and as pump sources for mid-IR generation [6,7]. In particular, TDF emission at 1907nm or 1940nm is used to excite holmium-doped yttrium aluminium garnets (Ho-YAG) [8], yttrium lithium fluoride (Ho-YLF) lasers [9], and holmium-doped fiber lasers [10]. Operation of TDFLs with two-level or quasi-three-level behavior at shorter wavelengths requires a higher inversion population [11]. From the point of view of laser configuration, it leads to a shorter fiber cavity, often at the expense of incomplete pump absorption and lower efficiency, or a special fiber waveguide design is required, e.g., distributed filtering of the long-wavelength part of the spectra [4] or improved gain at shorter wavelength by non-uniform Tm^{3+} doping of the fiber core [7]. Moreover, the spectroscopic properties may change significantly with increasing temperature; this change may hamper the intended inversion level and thus lead to the rise of ASE power [12] and/or excessive heat of polymer coating of the fiber, especially near splices [13,14], deteriorating fiber laser efficiency, output power level limits, as well as device reliability. Longer wavelengths in the range 2.05–2.1 μm can be used for eye-safe LIDAR, gas sensing

[15]. Additionally, low-phonon-energy hosts like tellurite glass enable emission up to 2.3 μm for molecular spectroscopy and amplifiers [16,17].

TDFs for high-power lasers are often made using modified chemical vapor deposition (MCVD) combined with solution doping methods to incorporate both Al_2O_3 and Tm^{3+} into the fiber core [18]. For high-power lasers with large mode areas, high doping concentrations require the so-called pedestal design to lower the effective numerical aperture (NA) and maintain single-mode operation. Since the pedestal has a lower effective NA in the fiber core, it acts as a high-NA waveguide itself, serving as both cladding for the active core and as a secondary, redundant core [19]. This secondary core is formed because the pedestal region is surrounded by a lower-refractive-index pure silica layer that serves as the standard fiber cladding. Consequently, the presence of a pedestal complicates fiber splicing and reduces fiber laser reliability. A fraction of the light that cannot be guided in the active core due to external perturbations or coupling issues becomes trapped in the pedestal and may negatively impact laser efficiency and reliability [13]. Recent research has focused on improving fabrication methods to maximize doping concentrations, such as vapor-phase deposition [20] or nanoparticle-doping techniques [21], as well as optimizing fiber design for power scaling and reliability [22], including pedestal-free designs [7,23]. To achieve such a design, the stack-and-draw (SAD) technique—adapted for rare-earth-ion (RE)-doped fibers [24] is used. The SAD technique enables the fabrication of complex, non-circular, or microstructured RE-doped fibers by stacking doped rods and/or capillaries into a preform before drawing. It can be used for preparing fiber lasers for dual-wavelength operation [25] or hollow-core fibers [26]. SAD can be used to fabricate fiber lasers due to its potential to scale the core area. The number of rods, both doped and undoped with RE-elements, can be easily adjusted, making SAD suitable for preparing fibers for single-mode operation [27] or LMA [28]. Fabricating TDFs with microstructured core by SAD can enable precise doping of high-concentration areas, facilitating a 2-for-1 process while maintaining a low average concentration across the fiber core. Note that diffusion processes have to be taken into account in designing the structure in order to maintain sufficiently high Tm^{3+} concentration even after diffusion takes place. Reducing the average Tm^{3+} concentration also helps prevent overheating, thereby improving the polymer coatings reliability [13]. Lower average concentration leads to slower variations of pump and signal powers along the fiber and in turn to lower heat load and fiber temperature [12]. The pedestal-free design presented in [23] has employed SAD to create nanoscale structures within the fiber core. The key advantage of nanostructuring is the ability to independently control the local Tm^{3+} concentration and the fiber core's effective refractive index. Instead of a uniform distribution, Tm^{3+} would be concentrated into nanorods. It also enables control over the core's effective refractive index by adjusting nanorod spacing when filling passive regions with pure silica. Optimizing the size, doping level, and spacing of nanorods permits control over the refractive index difference between the core and cladding without using any pedestal area. However, due to fact that individual rods inside such a nanostructured core are on level of tens of nanometers, diffusion of alumina described in [29] can have adverse effect on optical properties of such fibers as in the case of a nanostructured fiber [23], where a relatively low slope efficiency of 29% was achieved, partially due to the low concentration of Tm^{3+} in the nanorods, which was close to the threshold for cross-relaxation and due to the dopant diffusion. Additionally, the combination of a low average Tm^{3+} concentration across the fiber cross-section and high background losses at a level of 200 dB/km prevented higher efficiency.

In this work, we present a proof-of-concept for fabricating what are believed to be novel TDFs with a structured core and a high local concentration of Tm^{3+} , i.e., with minimized effect of diffusion, while maintaining a lower average concentration across the core. The proposed microstructured core has individual doped rods with a diameter of 2 μm , which is significantly larger than the 71 nm reported in [23], and distances between doped rods above 1 μm , which is larger than the diffusion occurring during the drawing process at 1900 $^\circ\text{C}$ [29]. Two designs

have been proposed: one composed of seven Tm-doped rods arranged in a hexagonal lattice to simulate a circular core. The second structure consists of six Tm-doped rods placed around one doped with Al_2O_3 , forming a ring similar to that shown in [7], designed to favor gain at shorter wavelengths, e.g., at 1907nm. These designs were proposed with the main aim of reducing heat load and, in this way, improving the cooling of the fiber laser and optimizing laser efficiency, while keeping low background losses in the fibers. Using the SAD technique, two fibers were fabricated and comparing the optical and laser properties of both fiber lasers shows that they can achieve 52% SE at 1907nm relative to absorbed power and 54% SE at 1940nm, making them suitable as an excitation sources for Ho-YAG and Ho-YLF lasers.

2. Fiber preparation

Two types of initial preforms were prepared similarly to [21,30] using the MCVD method combined with nanoparticle doping, allowing higher Al_2O_3 content and therefore higher concentration of Tm^{3+} [31]. The first was doped with Tm^{3+} and Al_2O_3 , and the second with only Al_2O_3 . Tm-doped initial preform had a Tm^{3+} concentration of 13000 mol ppm and 7.75 mol% Al_2O_3 . The doped core of the preform had a diameter of 1.4 mm. Preform doped only with Al_2O_3 had an initial concentration of 9.8 mol%. The doped core of the preform had a diameter of 1.45 mm. The preforms were etched in concentrated hydrofluoric acid to remove part of the silica cladding and then elongated into 330 μm canes. F300 tubes and rods were drawn to appropriate diameters, and using the SAD technique, the final preform was assembled according to the designs illustrated in Fig. 1(A) and 1(B). The fiber core was assembled using 330 μm canes doped with Tm^{3+} (blue circles) and Al_2O_3 (red circle), as shown in the insets of Fig. 1(A) and 1(B). The assembled final preforms were drawn into fibers at 1900 °C. During drawing, fibers were coated with a polymer coating XPC 373 with a refractive index of 1.373. The cladding numerical aperture was 0.48. The drawn fibers were further designated TDF-7Tm and TDF-6 \times 1Ring. Local Tm^{3+} concentration in each Tm-doped rod in both fibers was 13000 mol ppm. Average concentration of Tm^{3+} in TDF-7Tm calculated from the cross-section doped areas against the cross-section of the whole core from SEM, shown in the inset of Fig. 2(A), was 4850 mol ppm, and for TDF-6 \times 1Ring, the average concentration of Tm^{3+} across the core was 4160 mol ppm.

Fig. 1. A) Design of TDF-7Tm, B) Design of TDF-6 \times 1Ring.

3. Characterization of fibers and laser measurements

The overall macroscopic appearance of the fiber end face and detailed characterization of the fiber's core were obtained using the Scanning electron microscope (SEM) device TESCAN LYRA3 GM with a backscattered electron detector; the fiber sample was coated with a 20 nm thick layer of carbon. The appearance of the face of the drawn TDFs can be seen in Figs. 2. The fiber's core has a diameter of approximately 9.5 μm , with a silica cladding measuring 131 μm . In Fig. 2(A), the core contains seven separated bright spots representing Tm^{3+} -doped regions.

Fig. 2. SEM of whole fiber with an inset of a close look at the core of fiber A) TDF-7Tm, B) TDF-6 × 1Ring.

The core diameter was measured as the diameter of a circumscribed circle around all seven rods. A closer look at the fiber core through SEM is shown in the inset of Fig. 2(A), which indicates that the Tm^{3+} -doped areas have a diameter of about $2.2 \mu\text{m}$. Figure 2(B) displays six bright spots surrounding one darker area of Al_2O_3 . This contrast results from the presence of heavier Tm^{3+} ions compared to the undoped Al_2O_3 region. The inset in Fig. 2(B), showing the fiber core, clearly reveals a ring structure. Non-circular shape of six Tm-doped areas which form circle in both fibers is due to the flow of material attempting to fill the void (see dark parts in Fig. 1(A) and 1(B)) during the drawing of the optical fiber. Taking into account the diameter of the doped area in Tm-doped and Al_2O_3 (1.4 mm) and the size of the doped areas from the insets of Figs. 2(A), (B), there is a very small change in diameter, below $0.1 \mu\text{m}$, compared to the theoretical values derived from the draw-down ratio of 647.

The concentration of OH- groups was measured using a halogen broadband source and transmission spectra of tested fibers were detected by an Ando AQ6317B monochromator-based spectrometer over the expected spectral range, with spectral resolution of 2 nm. An approximately 110-meter-long section of fiber was used for TDF-7Tm, and ~200 m of fiber for TDF6 × 1Ring to estimate the concentration of OH groups, using a modified cutback method. The OH- content (for both) fibers was estimated as 0.73 mol ppm from the attenuation of 46 dB/km at the 1383-nm peak. To determine the OH- concentration, we used the equation $62.7 \text{ dB}/(\text{ppm} \times \text{km})$ at the OH- peak in silica-based fibers [32,33].

The fibers' refractive index profile (RIP) was measured using an optical fiber analyzer IFA-100 (Interfiber Analysis Inc.) with a laser source emitting at 979 nm. A 1D scan and 2D tomography were performed. For TDF-7Tm, the refractive index difference (RID) between the doped areas and the cladding is 7×10^{-3} , with a core diameter of approximately $9.5 \mu\text{m}$.

The 2D tomography zoomed into the core area displays seven distinct sections representing Tm-doped areas. For TDF-6 × 1Ring 1D (see Fig. 3(A)), the average RID is 8×10^{-3} , with the central area reaching 14.5×10^{-3} (Fig. 3(A)). This matches the 2D tomography, which shows a ring structure (Fig. 3(B)). Note that the IFA spatial resolution is about $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, which clearly influences the resolution of individual rods in the core.

For both fibers and both designed wavelengths, numerical modeling has been carried out to calculate numerical aperture (NA), mode-field diameter (MFD), and beam quality M^2 in the x and y axes. The beam quality factor M^2 was calculated by the method introduced in [34]

Values of NA for both fibers and wavelengths from Table 1 show that the structure with the theoretical refractive-index profile has $\text{NA} = 0.10$, estimated from the average refractive index in the $10 \mu\text{m}$ core. The resulting values from Table 1 of M^2 for both fibers and both wavelengths

Fig. 3. A) 1D RIP of TDF-7Tm and TDF-6 × 1Ring, B) 2D RIP TDF-7Tm and TDF-6 × 1Ring.

are below 1.2 in both orthogonal x and y directions, and thus the beam can be regarded as quasi-Gaussian.

Table 1. Parameters of simulated field profiles in TDF-7Tm rod and TDF-6 × 1Ring fibers

Fiber type	Wavelength [nm]	NA [-]	MFD [μm]	M^2_x [-]	M^2_y [-]
TDF-7Tm	1907	0.1012	13.08	1.152	1.162
	1940	0.1012	13.32	1.150	1.159
TDF-6 × 1Ring	1907	0.1026	12.53	1.155	1.165
	1940	0.1026	12.76	1.133	1.163

The impact of heat load is demonstrated quantitatively through fiber laser simulation results based on the numerical model described in [12]. Three fiber core types are compared: the standard TDF fiber with a circular core and two TDF fibers with microstructured cores, all having a core diameter of $d_c = 10 \mu\text{m}$. Pump power is set to $P_p = 100 \text{ W}$, and the fiber length is chosen to maximize output power. The average concentration of Tm^{3+} , N_{avg} , was taken from the calculated values for the structured fibers TDF-7Tm and TDF-6 × 1Ring, while 13000 mol ppm was assumed for the standard TDF fiber. The maximum heat load Q was calculated for all fibers. The results in Table 2 clearly show that the maximum heat load decreases as the average concentration decreases.

Table 2. Average concentration and maximum heat load in TDF fibers obtained from simulations.

Fiber type	N_{avg} [mol ppm]	Q [W/m]
TDF-standard	13000	22.1
TDF-7Tm	4850	12.5
TDF-6 × 1Ring	4160	11.0

Both fibers were characterized by their spectral absorption. A tungsten-halogen lamp was used as a broadband radiation source. To determine the core absorption, we employed a modified cutback method [35], where the transmission properties of the corresponding section of the active fiber, which was pigtailed from both sides with suitable passive fibers, and a reference fiber of the same type as the pigtailed, were measured and then compared. Absorption spectra were recorded with a Thorlabs OSA203C spectrometer over 1000–2600 nm, with a resolution of approximately 1 cm ($\sim 0.4 \text{ nm}$). The measured absorption spectra of both TDFs are shown in

Fig. 4(A). The shape of the depicted peaks is comparable with absorption peaks stated in the literature for Thulium-doped fiber lasers [4,36], confirming the presence of Tm^{3+} in the fiber core. Ground-state absorptions were measured at 99.3 dB/m at 1640 nm for TDF- 7Tm and 85.56 dB/m for the TDF 6×1 Ring structure. These values are comparable to those obtained for MCVD solid-core thulium fiber lasers used as broadband amplifiers [4].

Fig. 4. A) Core absorption of TDF-7Tm and TDF- 6×1 Ring, B) Cladding absorption of TDF-7Tm and TDF- 6×1 Ring.

Background losses (attenuation) were measured using the standard cut-back method with a long fiber piece of 184 m for TDF-7Tm and 132 m for TDF- 6×1 Ring and a short fiber piece of 2 m for both fibers under the constant launched condition. A broadband halogen lamp, bare fiber adapters, and a monochromator-based spectrometer (Ando, AQ6317B with a spectral resolution of 2 nm) were used. Excitation of the whole face of the fiber was used during the characterization. Measured minimum values of attenuation of 66 dB/km for TDF-7Tm and 55 dB/km for TDF- 6×1 Ring, both at 840 nm, show that these values are comparable with fibers produced by MCVD [31] and approximately 3.5 times lower compared to nanostructured fiber [23].

Cladding absorption is shown in Fig. 4(B). The spectral region around the emission wavelength of the laser diode (around 790 nm) was measured using a broadband tungsten-halogen lamp, and transmitted intensities were detected with an Ando AQ6317B monochromator-based spectrometer over 600-900 nm, with a spectral resolution of 2 nm. For cladding absorption measurements, several-meter-long sections were spliced to passive multimode fibers to excite the larger cladding regions, and a modified cutback method was used. Subsequently, the cladding absorption values can be used to estimate the optimal length of the laser cavity. Relatively low absorption values (<1 dB/m) indicated the need to use longer resonators (\sim 10 m).

The samples were characterized by fluorescence lifetime according to the procedure shown in detail in [31]. The 3F_4 lifetime, corresponding to emission near 2 μ m, was measured under in-band pumping at 1620 nm using a diode source. The emission was detected by an InGaAs (Hamamatsu) photodiode. The measured fibers were approximately 1 mm long, and emission was detected from the side in order to suppress the influence of amplified spontaneous emission and reabsorption.

Measured lifetimes for different pumping powers are shown in Fig. 5(A) and 5(C) for TDF-7Tm and TDF- 6×1 Ring, respectively. Decay times at different pumping powers are depicted in Fig. 5(B) and 5(D) for TDF-7Tm and TDF- 6×1 Ring, respectively. From the obtained measurements, it can be seen that at low pump powers, the fluorescence decay exhibited single-exponential behavior, indicating a homogeneous distribution of Tm^{3+} ions within both fiber cores. As the excitation power increased, the decay curves deviated from this behavior, and the measured decay time, obtained from the 1/e intensity on the normalized curve, shortened, which can be

attributed to the growing influence of energy-transfer (ET) processes between neighboring ions. The measured decay time saturated at low powers, and the fluorescence lifetime extrapolated to zero power was nearly identical in both samples, ranging from 515 to 520 μs . As stated in [31], fluorescence lifetimes above 500 μs in aluminosilicate fibers generally indicate a favorable low-phonon environment for Tm^{3+} ions and show promise for efficient laser operation.

Fig. 5. A) lifetimes of TDF-7Tm at different pumping powers B) fluorescence decay times at different pumping powers of TDF-7Tm, C) lifetime of TDF-6 \times 1Ring at different pumping powers D) fluorescence decay times at different pumping powers of TDF-6 \times 1Ring. The decay times were fitted for both fibers using Eq. (1) in Ref. [15].

Laser performance of structured-core fibers was tested in a linear laser configuration, as depicted in Fig. 6. The TDFs were pumped with a 792 nm laser diode (BWT, 105/125 μm), with limited pump power up to 45 W. A high-reflectivity fiber Bragg gratings (FBGs) were used, reflecting at 1907 nm (Advanced Fiber Resources, 10/130 μm) and at 1940 nm (TeraXion, 10/130 μm), respectively. The output coupler was created by Fresnel reflection ($\sim 4\%$) from a perpendicularly cleaved fiber end. The output power was measured using a dichroic mirror (Crytur), Thorlabs S425C-L, and a Thorlabs S142C power meter.

Fig. 6. Experimental set-up for measurement of laser performance of TDF-7Tm and TDF-6 \times 1Ring,

Figure 7(A) shows the laser output power for TDF-7Tm as a function of absorbed pump power at 1907 and 1940nm. At 1940nm, the maximum output power reached 24.8 W, with a slope efficiency (SE) of 54.1% and a laser threshold of 1.8 W. At 1907nm, the maximum output power reached 15.6 W, with an SE of 51.9% and the same laser threshold of 1.8 W. Very similar values were obtained for TDF-6 × 1ring, as shown in Fig. 7(B).

Fig. 7. A) Laser performance with respect to absorbed power for TDF 7Tm B) Laser performance with respect to absorbed power for TDF-6 × 1Ring

At 1940nm, the maximum output power reached 24.7 W, with an SE of 54.8% and a laser threshold of 1.8 W. At 1907nm, a maximum output power of 16.6 W was achieved at the same pump power, with a laser threshold of 1.70 W and a slightly lower SE of 51.8%. No visible roll-off, saturation, or parasitic lasing was observed in any of the laser curves or laser spectra, indicating that the maximum output power can be further increased with a more powerful pump source.

The optimized fiber lengths were similar, ranging from 10 to 12 m, as shown in Table 3, along with SE values for each fiber and wavelength. Using the cut-back method, the optimal fiber lengths (for both fibers) were determined by the maximum slope efficiency with respect to absorbed pump power. These fiber lengths were determined by the relatively low cladding pump absorption of about 1.1 dB/m at 793 nm. Using the method for determining quantum efficiency and background losses [37], we calculated losses exceeding 200 dB/km for both TDFs. With fiber lengths over 10 meters, the impact of length becomes significant, which may explain the lower SE. Despite a longer resonator, no parasitic lasing was observed, and laser emission remained stable. These SE values are higher than the 29% SE obtained for a nanostructured thulium-doped fiber [23]. Together with measured lower background losses and a reduced effect of RE diffusion when using much larger Tm^{3+} doped rod elements, these values demonstrate that the proposed structure exhibits promising properties suitable for high-power applications, even at shorter wavelengths.

Table 3. Values of slope efficiencies for both TDFs at optimal length for 1907nm and 1940nm

	1907nm	1940nm
TDF-7Tm	51.9% / 11.5 m	54% / 12.5 m
TDF-6 × 1Ring	51.8% / 12 m	54.8% / 10 m

4. Conclusions

In this work, two TDF designs were successfully fabricated using the MCVD method with nanoparticle doping and the stack-and-draw technique. Both fiber types exhibited well-defined pedestal-free refractive index profiles. Laser experiments using a linear laser configuration showed stable emission at 1907nm and 1940nm, with SE reaching 52% at both wavelengths. The absence of parasitic lasing, even with extended resonator lengths, confirms the effectiveness of the design. These results demonstrate the potential of pedestal-free fibers with a structured core to improve laser reliability while maintaining high fiber laser efficiency, thus offering a promising fabrication route for high-power fiber lasers in the 2 μ m spectral region.

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References

1. M. N. Zervas and C. A. Codemard, "High power fiber lasers: A review," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Quantum Electron.* **20**(5), 219–241 (2014).
2. M. Grábner, B. Švejkarová, J. Aubrecht, *et al.*, "Analytical model of thulium-doped fiber laser pumped by two-for-one process," *J. Lightwave Technol.* **42**(8), 2938–2944 (2024).
3. S. Chen, Y. Jung, S. Alam, *et al.*, "Ultra-short wavelength operation of thulium-doped fiber amplifiers and lasers," *Opt. Express* **27**(25), 36699 (2019).
4. J. Aubrecht, J. Pokorný, B. Švejkarová, *et al.*, "Broadband thulium fiber amplifier for spectral region located beyond the L-band," *Opt. Express* **32**(10), 17932 (2024).
5. S. Chen, Y. Chen, K. Liu, *et al.*, "All-fiber short-wavelength tunable mode-locked fiber laser using normal dispersion thulium-doped fiber," *Opt. Express* **28**(12), 17570 (2020).
6. C. W. Rudy, M. J. F. Dignonnet, and R. L. Byer, "Advances in 2- μ m Tm-doped mode-locked fiber lasers," *Optic. Fiber Technol.* **20**(6), 642–649 (2014).
7. M. J. Barber, P. C. Shardlow, P. Barua, *et al.*, "Nested-ring doping for highly efficient 1907nm short-wavelength cladding-pumped thulium fiber lasers," *Opt. Lett.* **45**(19), 5542 (2020).
8. Z. He, T. Yu, J. Ren, *et al.*, "A high-energy Ho:YAG amplifier pumped by a 1907nm Tm-doped fiber laser," *Appl. Phys. B* **132**(1), 8 (2026).
9. B. Lei, L. Zhang, S. Yang, *et al.*, "Near diffraction-limited in-band pumped Ho:YLF composite thin disk laser at 2 μ m," *Opt. Express* **33**(4), 7569 (2025).
10. R. Švejkar, B. Švejkarová, M. Kamrádek, *et al.*, "All-fiber core-pumped Ho-doped laser with 95 W output power and high efficiency," *Opt. Express* **34**(6), 10971 (2026).
11. G. Frith, A. Carter, B. Samson, *et al.*, "Design considerations for short-wavelength operation of 790-nm-pumped Tm-doped fibers," *Appl. Opt.* **48**(27), 5072 (2009).
12. M. Grábner, B. Švejkarová, J. Aubrecht, *et al.*, "Rise of amplified spontaneous emission in high-power thulium-doped fiber lasers and amplifiers due to self-heating," *Opt. Laser Technol.* **180**, 111428 (2025).
13. M. Michalska, P. Honzatko, P. Grzes, *et al.*, "Thulium-doped 1940- and 2034-nm fiber amplifiers: Towards highly efficient, high-power all-fiber laser systems," *J. Lightwave Technol.* **42**(1), 339–346 (2024).
14. B. Švejkarová, M. Grábner, J. Aubrecht, *et al.*, "Thulium fiber lasers with longitudinally modified concentration," *High Pow. Laser Sci Eng.* **13**, e71 (2025).
15. F. Liu, P. Liu, X. Feng, *et al.*, "Tandem-pumped, tunable thulium-doped fiber laser in 21 μ m wavelength region," *Opt. Express* **27**(6), 8283 (2019).
16. R. Xu, Y. Tian, L. Hu, *et al.*, "2 μ m spectroscopic investigation of Tm³⁺-doped tellurite glass fiber," *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* **357**(11-13), 2489–2493 (2011).
17. S. V. Muravyev, E. A. Anashkina, A. V. Andrianov, *et al.*, "Dual-band Tm³⁺-doped tellurite fiber amplifier and laser at 1.9 μ m and 2.3 μ m," *Sci. Rep.* **8**(1), 16164 (2018).
18. A. Sincore, J. D. Bradford, J. Cook, *et al.*, "High Average Power Thulium-Doped Silica Fiber Lasers: Review of Systems and Concepts," *IEEE J. Sel. Topics Quantum Electron.* **24**(3), 1–8 (2018).
19. K. Tankala, B. Samson, A. Carter, *et al.*, "New developments in high power eye-safe LMA fibers," in A. J. W. Brown, J. Nilsson, D. J. Harter, and A. Tünnermann, eds. *Proc. SPIE 6102, Fiber Lasers III: Technology, Systems, and Applications*, (2006), p. 610206.

20. N. J. Ramírez-Martínez, M. Núñez-Velázquez, A. A. Umnikov, *et al.*, “Highly efficient thulium-doped high-power laser fibers fabricated by MCVD,” *Opt. Express* **27**(1), 196 (2019).
21. M. Kamrádek, I. Kašík, J. Aubrecht, *et al.*, “Nanoparticle and solution doping for efficient holmium fiber lasers,” *IEEE Photonics J.* **11**(5), 1–10 (2019).
22. I. Barton, M. Franczyk, P. Peterka, *et al.*, “Optimization of erbium and ytterbium concentration in nanostructured core fiber for dual-wavelength fiber lasers,” in *Specialty Optical Fibres*, K. Kalli, A. Mendez, and P. Peterka, eds. (SPIE, 2023), 12573, p. 1257311.
23. P. Peterka, J. Aubrecht, D. Pysz, *et al.*, “Development of pedestal-free large mode area fibers with Tm³⁺ doped silica nanostructured core,” *Opt. Express* **31**(26), 43004 (2023).
24. W. J. Wadsworth, R. M. Percival, G. Bouwmans, *et al.*, “High power air-clad photonic crystal fibre laser,” *Opt. Express* **11**(1), 48–53 (2003).
25. I. Kasik, I. Barton, M. Kamrádek, *et al.*, “Doped and structured silica optical fibres for fibre laser sources,” *Opt. Commun.* **577**, 131437 (2025).
26. F. Poletti, “Nested antiresonant nodeless hollow core fiber,” *Opt. Express* **22**(20), 23807–23828 (2014).
27. I. Barton, P. Peterka, M. Grabner, *et al.*, “Structured ytterbium and erbium -doped silica fiber for dual wavelength laser operation,” *J. Lightwave Technol.* (2026) in print.
28. Y. Wang, R. Buczyński, K. Krupa, *et al.*, “Nanostructured active fiber for mode-locked and Q-switched all-fiber laser systems,” *J. Lightwave Technol.* **43**(15), 7322–7328 (2025).
29. J. Kobelke, K. Schuster, J. Bierlich, *et al.*, “Germania and alumina dopant diffusion and viscous flow effects at preparation of doped optical fibers,” *Adv. Electr. Electron. Eng.* **15**(1), 2009 (2017).
30. M. Kamrádek, J. Aubrecht, P. Vařák, *et al.*, “Energy transfer coefficients in thulium-doped silica fibers,” *Opt. Mater. Express* **11**(6), 1805–1814 (2021).
31. P. Vařák, M. Leich, M. Kamrádek, *et al.*, “Nanoparticle doping and molten-core methods towards highly thulium-doped silica fibers for 0.79 μm -pumped 2 μm fiber lasers – A fluorescence lifetime study,” *J. Lumines.* **275**, 120835 (2024).
32. O. Humbach, H. Fabian, U. Grzesik, *et al.*, “Analysis of OH absorption bands in synthetic silica,” *J. Non-cryst. solids* **203**, 19–26 (1996).
33. J. Aubrecht, P. Peterka, P. Koška, *et al.*, “Self-swept holmium fiber laser near 2100 nm,” *Opt. Express* **25**(4), 4120 (2017).
34. S. Liao, M. Gong, and H. Zhang, “Theoretical calculation of beam quality factor of large-mode-area fiber amplifiers,” *Laser Phys.* **19**(3), 437–444 (2009).
35. B. Jiříčková, M. Grábner, C. Jauregui, *et al.*, “Temperature-dependent cross section spectra for thulium-doped fiber lasers,” *Opt. Lett.* **48**(3), 811–814 (2023).
36. S. D. Agger and J. H. Povlsen, “Emission and absorption cross section of thulium doped silica fibers,” *Opt. Express* **14**(1), 50 (2006).
37. M. P. Buckthorpe and W. A. Clarkson, “Simple method for determining quantum efficiency and background propagation loss in thulium-doped fibres,” *Appl. Phys. B* **129**(9), 142 (2023).